

Labeo umbratus

Moggel

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

© R Bills

Group: Bony Fish

Size: Maximum length is 50 cm

Distribution:

This species is endemic to Southern Africa, with populations split between the Orange-Vaal River system in the north and eight isolated river systems from the Gouritz to the Nahoon River in the south.

Importance:

The Moggel is a freshwater fish endemic to Southern Africa. It is important for commercial and subsistence fisheries, angling, aquaculture, and physiological research. The current classification of Least Concern overlooks the species' taxonomic complexity. Preliminary phylogeographic results indicated distinct, allopatric lineages with morphological differences, suggesting multiple species within this taxon.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 23.52 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 3.25 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome Length: 1.06 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.4% [Single: 94.5%, Duplicated: 3.9%]

Assembly N50: 468.45 kilobases

Contig number: 18 268

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